

Research

A study to enhance the implementation of safety engineering in the construction of Oil and Gas projects in Yemen

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Abstract: Risk assessment is one of the most critical methodologies used in the safety engineering system in oil and gas construction projects that require high levels of precaution in construction activities such as pilling, materials fabrication, and structure installation. The main purpose of risk assessment is to provide full protection to the four main elements that are crucial to the oil industry: People, Environment, Assets and Reputation (PEAR). Any failure or defect in the risk assessment implementation can potentially lead to catastrophes not only during the construction stage but also in the advanced stages such as operation and productions. Historically, in oil and gas construction projects many oil spills and blow outs occurred due to lack of efficient risk assessment in the construction phase, resulting in financial loss and human capitals. The aim of this research is to enhance the implementation of safety engineering systems in the oil and gas industry construction projects through risk assessment application in the YEMEN. The main outcomes of this research study expose a gap in the understanding and the practices of risk assessment methods between management and workers, especially with regard to human factors effects on safety performance.

Keywords: Safety and Risk Assessment, Hazard Evaluations, Hazard guidelines.

1. Aim of the research

The aim of this research is to enhance the implementation of safety engineering systems in the oil and gas industry construction projects through risk assessment application in the Yemen. Firstly, the aim is achieved via conducting a questionnaire to determine the current defects in the risk assessment applied methodology in the safety engineering system. Secondly, interviews are conducted with safety construction professionals to examine top risk factors in Yemen oil and gas construction projects.

2. Introduction

Construction is a very dynamic and complex industry, facing numerous challenges. According to Reyes et al. (2014), Health and Safety (HS) concept can play a vital role in preventing and mitigating all critical risk factors and this only can be achieved by ensuring the implementation of HS matters in the whole construction project life cycle. Reyes et al., believe that construction industry has a high accident rate compared to other industries due to the complexity of construction factors, possessing a social, human and economic dimension. Risk assessment is one of the most vital elements in addressing all the HS engineering matters of the construction building project life cycle where internal factors can have direct influence on the risk assessment implementations. Internal factors that may affect the risk assessment implementation in the construction company are insufficient communication, perceived budget viability and production/time pressure. Coble et al., propose best management practices that are mostly related to management leadership which can increase the awareness level internally at construction organization. In the end of their research, the authors encourage researchers to study the effects of external factors such as new technologies and their effect on the risk assessment implementation in the construction building projects. Table 1 represents a crude oil production in Yemen is last 20 years

Table 1: Crude Oil production in Yemen since 1984

Year	Production rate Million (b/d)
1984	0.6
1986	0.7
1989	0.9
1990	1.7
1991	1.9
1998	2.0
2016	1.1

3. Research methodology

The aim of this study is to evaluate the implementation of safety engineering system in oil and gas construction through risk assessment in Yemen. To do so, four objectives should be examined, where these objectives contain three different aspects; technical, procedural, and behavioral. Each objective has different methodology in order to be achieved in this research conducted an experiment to evaluate risk analysis and risk assessment approaches that are applied in the petroleum industry in Norway. They used a survey to determine the risk analysis methods of different oil and gas construction companies in Norway and to expose the challenges in the risk assessment.

Similar approach will be employed and a survey will be utilized to determine the risk analysis and identification methods of the Yemen oil and gas construction rigs, along with their weaknesses that affect the implementation of risk assessment. In addition this research will have combination of exploratory and descriptive methodology approaches. For example, in the exploratory feature, one of the questionnaire objectives is to explore the implementation problem

to provide insights into and comprehension for more accurate examination. Furthermore, since this research covers the behavioral attributes of the individual worker in the construction site, a description of characteristics and functions is required which gives this study a descriptive trace in the methodology stage. To ensure the implementation of risk assessment in construction, there should be a continuous follow-up plan that monitors the quality of execution in all the basic five stages of construction: initiating, concept, planning, organization, and finishing as explained in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Risk assessment life cycle in construction

4. Analyzing the results and framework

The questionnaires start with demographic questions such as age, employer, gender and job position where these kinds of questions will provide a better approach and understanding in the result analyzing stage. This will result on providing an effective integrated framework for the targeted populations in this research. The first question in the general demographic question section starts with inquiring the type of the construction company that the employer works in it (e.g. owner, vendor, and contractor). The majority of the responses in this questionnaire came from owner companies represented by government companies such as Yemen Marine Operating Company and international contractor companies such as Consolidated Contractors Company (CCC). An estimated population number was determined to enable the calculation of an optimum sample size for the questionnaire.

4.1 Statically significance

In this research work, Z score test was applied to verify the statistical significance for the following statements in the questionnaire where several scholars such as Goncalves et al., (2007) suggest using Z score test (two tailed) with stratified random sampling method as it provides the flexibility on assigning the weights for the variables. Supporting that, Lee et al., (2007) use Z

score test as a statistical approach to determine the level of safety culture in different industries including construction.

4.3 Analyzing the results

Figure 2.1: Type of the construction company.

Figure 2.1 shows that 51% of the respondents are working with owner companies, 45% with the contractor companies and only 4% working with vendors companies. These numbers reflect the realistic employment landscape of Yemen oil and gas construction industry in which most employees at the construction site at oil and gas rigs are either from owner or contractor companies. A vast majority of the responses came from males (92%) as shown in Figure 2.2. This is due to the nature of the culture and physical requirements of the construction laborers role.

Figure 2.2: Employee gender.

Most employees participating in this survey were of the age between 20 and 50 as Fig. 2.3 explicates. Of this, 30-40 years old employees are the majority (33%). The explanation for that is that many employees in the oil and gas construction field usually get to the seniority or managerial post when they are 40-50 years old. As explained above, work in the oil and gas construction projects demands physical and mental wellbeing and as such, many employees tend to retire when they reach age 50. This explains why only 7% of the targeted population was above 50 years old. For the fresh construction workers, they start their career at a very young age, ranging from 17 to 19 years old.

However, this questionnaire displays that both experienced and fresh construction laborers share the same education levels, which is a basic level. Figure 2.4 illustrates that most construction laborers find it very difficult to communicate in English, which poses a severe challenge to understand the safety producers and manuals made available at the construction rig.

Figure 2.3: Employee age.

By comparison, supervisors and administrative employees boast high school or university diplomas which assist them in conducting the documentation work in their job duties.

Figure 2.4: Education level of employees.

Bachelor and Master Degree holders occupy the leading roles in the organization, such as fresh engineers all the way up to senior engineers and senior manager posts that have a significant authority at the construction field. It can be seen from Figure. 2.4 that there are three main classifications with respect to the education level in construction:

- Basic education (70%)
- Diploma (18%)
- Bachelor or Master Degrees (10%)

Employees with PhD degrees usually work in the corporate offices and they come to the construction rig as temporary assignment to conducted courses for other employees as part of the employee development plans in the organization. This explains why only 2% employees hold PhD degrees.

In terms of job position demographics, there are two classifications to select: end-user (labourer and technician), and senior staff (managers and senior managers) as evidenced by Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Job position for the employee.

The results in Figure 2.5 simulate the reality of job position distribution in the most construction companies, especially in YEMEN. To illustrate, Al-Kaabi and Hadipriono (2003) mention that the majority of the employee of the construction companies in YEMEN are the construction workers, which is the reason why the level of risk exposure and accident rate is high in YEMEN. However, the authors believe that even if the mainstream of the employees at the construction organizations are labourers, the focus of safety engineering implementation should not be only narrowed for this group but should involve all the organization employees from the top management to the end users level to ensure safety culture at the construction site.

Figure 2.6: Construction worker are involved in safety committees and planning.

Safety responsibility in construction is so critical where many senior staff in oil and gas try to avoid taking or even sharing it. This is due to the legal consequences that may occur after any potential accident. Behm (2005) mentions that avoiding the safety responsibilities is the main reason why many construction employees do not implement the safety engineering system. The author believes that safety responsibility should be defined in the early stages of the construction project, especially the design stages where it can be applied via different. For example, during the hazard identification process, the author suggests to specifically mention the safety responsibility for each potential hazard that may cause accidents at the construction sites. Moreover, Behm claims that declaring safety responsibility at the construction project helps the safety professionals in their root cause analysis i.e. following the chain of actions and interviewing people will be more accurate and precise.

Figure 2.7: Top management actively involved and take direct responsibility of safety incidents.

Figure 2.7 shows that 64% of the respondents believe that their management does not take any direct safety responsibility in the case of an incident at the construction site. This produces the feeling of lack of support from management towards the end-user workers. The 24% who hold a contradictory view are placed in managerial positions, thus exposing another major gap between the management and workers in the oil and gas construction. Korman (1999) says that the absence of management responsibility to safety accidents will mar the worker safety performance and may encourage them to practice unhealthy acts, such as not reporting accidents. Thevendran & Mawdesley, (2004) conduct an experiment that try to examine how construction organizations in critical industries such as oil and gas perceive human factors in their projects. The authors believe that evolution of human factors for construction project is crucial and there is a generic acknowledgement that human factors are the most important elements that can ensure the success and safety of construction activities. The exploratory study of their research show that there are many influences that can impact the interaction between the human and machines and this can cause deterioration for safety performance and increase the frequency of risk at the construction site.

Figure 2.8: Human factors are always considered in the hazard identification stage.

The authors explain that these influences arise from different sources inside the construction firm, including management leadership, mind-set and education/training. For instance, if the organizations share the ownership with the employees or hire a welfare officer, it will increase the sense of belonging and that will help to reduce the potential existence of human factors risk in the site. Figure 2.8 sheds that most respondents (59%) do not agree that their construction firms are examining human factors in the hazard identification analysis which can impact the efficiency of risk assessment. Haslam et al., (2005) believe that many of construction projects in high risk industry such as oil and gas do not involve assessing human factors in the early stage of the risk assessment which affect the implementation of the safety engineering system.

Finally, the questionnaire asks the respondents two questions about the factors that can improve the safety engineering system inside oil and gas organizations. Usually the safety engineer system comprises of areas such as leadership, audits, regulations, planning and risk assessment. Fig. 63 shows that most respondents point to this risk assessment methods (46%) and Behavioural Base Safety Programme (33%) as the top areas that needed to improve, a result that

is consistent with the survey results. To illustrate this point, the questionnaire outcomes reveal the willingness of safety commitment in the oil and gas construction platform from the management level to the end users level, but external and internal factors inhibit its implementation. The same concept is reflected in regard to the BBS based on the respondent's answers at the end of the survey where a glaring ignorance towards BBS factors such as Human Factors (HF) and their role at safety engineering system implementation is highlighted.

Figure 2.9: Which area of safety engineering system in your company requires improvement.

The last question in the survey asks the employees about the most effective factor that can impact the mechanism of the safety engineering system for oil and gas construction industry. Here, poor decision-making was selected by 45% from the respondents. Koller (2005) mentions that factors such as poor communication, lack of sufficient and integrated examination will result in a weak risk assessment output that decision-maker will depend on. According to the author, this is why many of construction professionals in oil and gas industry consider poor decision-making is the real root cause for most incidents that occur in the site as shown in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10: which one from the following factors could be the most effective one in the safety engineering system implementation.

This questionnaire exposes several areas that directly influence the safety engineering systems, especially the risk assessment, varying from technical, procedural, and behavioral features. However, further investigation is necessary to understand the reasons and risk factors behind why these challenges exist inside the construction organization, particularly between senior management and labourers. Such an investigation will help reach the aim of this study i.e. providing an integrated framework to optimize the safety engineering system in the oil and gas industry. This can be approached through interviewing construction professionals who possess a complete view pertaining to the current barriers and issues for safety implementation at the construction sites.

4.4 Framework Development

Figure 2.11: Integrated Risk assessment framework for oil and gas construction projects

The aim of this study is to provide an integrated framework that can optimize the implementation of the safety engineering system through the usage of a risk assessment. Both the questionnaire and the interviews exposed the presently weak areas in the risk assessment application thereby aiding the selection of the framework inputs in this research. As shown in the Figure 2.11, there are three main sections employed as filters during the hazard identification stage in which each one of them has specific criteria. Such a focus will facilitate avoiding the kind generalizations practiced in most risk assessment sessions to cover all the possible scenarios that can occur with the existing hazards.

Each group has three standards that should clarify the identified hazard, its dimension and interaction mechanism with the wanted construction activity. Following this full examination, a regular risk assessment procedure is carried out where risk estimation and evaluation will be conducted in the General Risk Characterization stage. At the same time, risk monitoring will be involved in the all steps to facilitate a healthy communication between the parties, especially the management and end-users.

5. Conclusion & Recommendation

This study strives to optimize the safety performance at construction projects in the oil and gas fields through implementation of risk assessment. As can be gleaned from the literature review, many scholars elucidate their struggles with current applications of risk assessment and the needs for an integrated approach. The aim of this research is to involve all vital and contributable areas that can cause an accident as immediate or root source. Technical, procedural, and behavioral aspects were investigated with respect to the external and internal attributes that play a critical role in the oil and gas industry. Pervious risk assessment frameworks could not provide an integrated perspective to identify the full scope of the hazards at the construction site. To have an integrated view for better safety implementation, an integrated examination should be conducted. To determine the possible threats at the site, all the employees in the organization have been questioned through a survey that was distributed as a part of the field work in this research.

Since construction is a very practical field, especially in critical industry such as oil and gas, there is a need to examine how this Framework will be adopted and applied with the current situations. The evaluators expounded that the impact of the Framework is different from one employee to another depending on his/her role in the organization. For example, the evaluator claimed that the organization should prepare a plan that involves all employee categories: senior staff, Middle management, and workers. According to the evaluators, this provides each category to implement the Framework process in the rate and methodology that suits its function at the site. Additionally, the evaluators highly recommended continuous response to the workers 'feedbacks which improves the framework and its implementation. Moreover, to optimize the safety performance, the evaluator suggested several healthy practices which must be applied along with the Framework. For example, since equipment failures are very common at the construction site, having reliability engineer at the site can play a major factor to eliminate these unwanted events.

Finally, as part of the vitality of the end-user feed backs and visibility, this research stresses the importance of the Framework's welfare section. This is a new concept related to the risk assessment in construction with workers' welfare, boasting several advantages in adopting the framework. For example, when workers express their satisfaction with the welfare facilities, this provides an indication of their capability to learn and implement the Framework procedures. To maintain this healthy culture, it is important to encourage the end-users to be involved as key

participants in the welfare section during risk assessment and report any defect that could occur in the construction operation. As a result, the senior management in the organization will emphasize the workers' welfare as a factor in which it can enhance safety and production rate simultaneously.

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Main research directions: 1. Mine gas prevention; 2. Mine water inrush prevention.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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